

Table 2. Length and number of internodes in horizontal placement (HP) and upright position (URP) of shoots in water at 50 cm depth.^a

Variety	Length of internodes (cm)				Elongated internodes (no.)				Elongation score in >100 cm water ^b (from previous test)
	Control	HP	URP	Difference (HP-URP)	Control	HP	URP	Difference (HP-URP)	
<i>Floating rice</i>									
Jalmagna	97 a	134 a	101 a	33**	7.0 a	11.7 a	7.7 a	4.0**	1
Balsbish	78 c	109 b	87 b	22**	6.0 b	11.0 a	7.0 ab	4.0**	1
NDGR417	88 b	111 b	101 a	10**	6.0 b	9.0 b	6.7 bc	2.3**	1
<i>Elongating modern variety</i>									
NDGR150	60 d	79 c	68 c	11*	5.0 cd	7.0 b	5.3 d	1.7**	5
IR11141-6-1-4	38 e	58 d	39 d	19**	6.0 b	7.3 c	6.3 b	1.0**	5
IR11288-B-B-69-1	42 e	62 d	50 d	12**	5.7 bc	7.3 c	6.0 bc	1.3**	5
<i>Traditional deepwater</i>									
NDGR207	61 d	62 c	65	-3 ns	4.3 de	6.7 c	4.3 e	2.4*	5
<i>Nonelongating modern variety</i>									
IR36	26 f	43 e	28 f	15*	4.0 e	5.0 d	4.0 e	1.0**	9
IR42	21 f	37 e	25 c f	12*	4.0 e	5.0 d	4.0 e	1.0**	9
Av	57	77	62	15	5.3	7.8	5.8	2.0	
Comparison 2-M*S mean									
LSD (0.05)	7.63	0.83							
LSD (0.01)	10.16	1.11							

^a*, ** = significant at 5% and 1% levels, respectively; ns = not significant. In a column, figures followed by different letters significantly differ at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bBy the Standard evaluation system for rice.

The greater total internode lengths in HP treatments may be due to a more severe treatment when the submergence bar is moved 60 cm, relative to the 50-cm water depth increase in the URP treatment. This is consistent with the number of internodes from horizontally oriented shoots, which was greater than for URP plants.

Among the floating rices, plants in HP produced 9-12 internodes and those in the URP produced 7-8 internodes. The elongation scores of these varieties evaluated at >1-m water depth at Ghagharaghat, India, were comparable to those of HP shoots (data not presented).

The findings indicate that the horizontal orientation method sufficiently induced elongation and can be used to test plants for elongation potential. An advantage of this method is that deep flooding is not needed to test for internode elongation so it can be used to screen varieties or segregating populations. These benefits will need to be evaluated with respect to the greater surface area required for horizontal placement of plants. ■

Stress tolerance—adverse temperature

Chlorophyll fluorescence analysis (CFA) for assessing cold tolerance at anthesis in Nepalese indigenous rice genotypes

B. R. Sthapit, Crop Science Section, Lumle Regional Agricultural Research Centre, P.O. Box 1, Kaski, Pokhara, Nepal; and J. M. Wilson, School of Biological Sciences, University of Wales, Thoday Building, Bangor, Gwynedd LL57 2UW, UK

We screened eight rice genotypes (seven indigenous and one exotic) from the Himalayan region for sterile-type cold tolerance at anthesis using CFA (see table). The objective was to determine whether chlorophyll fluorescence, measured after a short period of chilling at the critical booting stage, would correlate with spikelet sterility.

During the process of photosynthesis, chlorophyll fluorescence is re-emitted from the chlorophylls associated with the

Cold tolerance ranking of rice cultivars at Pokhara, Nepal.

Variety	Altitude (m asl)	Field ranking for cold tolerance ^a	Origin
Chhomrong	1400-2000	CT at all growth stages	Nepal
Silange	1500-1800	CT at all growth stages	Nepal
Seto Takmare	1500-1700	CT at reproductive phase	Nepal
Rato Darmali	1600-1700	CT at late anthesis stage	Nepal
Kalopatle	1400-1500	CT at reproductive phase	Nepal
Bhatte	1200-1500	CWT at vegetative phase	Nepal
China 1039	1000-1200	CT at late anthesis stage	India
Marshi	900-1200	CS at all growth stages	Nepal

^aCT = cold tolerant, CWT = cold water tolerant, and CS = cold sensitive.

Relationship between chlorophyll fluorescence (Fv/Fm) measured after 5 d of chilling treatment at 17 °C and spikelet sterility (%) for 8 rice genotypes. Pokhara, Nepal.

therefore used as a good diagnostic probe for measuring cold stress. A healthy leaf generally gives a Fv/Fm value of about 0.80.

We grew the rice genotypes under glasshouse conditions (28/18 °C) until the booting stage. Plants were chilled for 5 d at 17 °C under a 10/14 h day/night cycle in a growth chamber, taken back to the glasshouse, and kept there at 23 °C to complete the crop cycle. Plants were given plant food Champax Formula No. 2 at 0.714 g/liter of tap water.

We measured chlorophyll fluorescence of the flag leaves after 5 d of chilling using a CF1000 fluorometer. Panicle sterility and other agronomic parameters were measured at harvest.

A significant negative correlation ($r = -0.89$) between Fv/Fm at booting and spikelet sterility (%) was found (see figure). This indicates that Fv/Fm can be used to predict spikelet fertility and is therefore a useful tool in screening for cold tolerance at anthesis.

Cold-tolerant varieties Silange, Chhomrong, Sinjali, Kalopatie, and Takmare had higher photochemical efficiency under chilling stress and the least spikelet sterility of the varieties tested. Cold-sensitive cultivars, such as Marshi, had smaller Fv/Fm values and the greatest degree of sterility (56.3%). Darmali and Bhatte, both known for cold tolerance at tillering, exhibited poor tolerance at anthesis (see figure).

Results from both field and growth chamber experiments suggest that relative ranking for cold tolerance can be based on absolute Fv/Fm values recorded after cold stress.

Further studies are planned in Nepal using this technique to study cold tolerance in segregating populations and in the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery. ■

reaction centers photosystem II (PSII). The onset of chilling injury in leaves is accompanied by a decrease in chlorophyll fluorescence. The ratio of variable fluorescence (Fv) to maximal fluorescence (Fm), termed as photochemical efficiency of PSII (Fv/Fm), is directly related to its quantum efficiency and is

Efficiency of natural selection against cold-induced sterility in bulked families

J. P. Tilquin, Crop Improvement Department, Agricultural Faculty, University of Burundi, P.O. Box 2940, Bujumbura; and J. F. Detry, Phytopathology Department, Institut des Sciences Agronomiques du Burundi (ISABU), Burundi

ISABU identified Yunnan 3 in 1980 as a relatively well-adapted variety for swamps at 1,300 to 1,650 m above sea level (m asl). Growing rice at this altitude is important for Burundi as it is a densely

populated country (206 humans/km²). International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery results, however, were disappointing. A breeding program was initiated to improve varietal diversification.

The isotherms of the area vary between 16 and 22 °C with frequent night temperatures as low as 10 °C. Cold-induced sterility is the major constraint.

We bulked reciprocal crosses in rapid generations at 800 m asl. Some families (Facagro 57 and Facagro 59) with narrow variability were subjected to natural selection in F₄₋₆ at 1,550 m asl at the 16 °C isotherm. The yields of the Facagro 57 and 59 families progressed annually,

Sterility of families derived from 2 hybrids subjected to natural selection from F₄ to F₆ at 16 °C isotherm.

partly because of lowered sterility. Facagro 57 originated from B2980b-Sr-2-6-2-3-2/IR24312-RR-19-3-B (45.7 and 83.7% parental sterility, respectively). Facagro 59 originated from IR24312-RR-19-3-B/NR10041-66-3-1 (83.7 and 70.8% parental sterility, respectively).

Sterility was estimated using a sample of 25 disease-free panicles (three replications) from the same site in a pluriannual trial that included Ambalalava, a well-adapted variety at 1,500 to 1,700 m asl in Madagascar.

The figure illustrates the evolution of sterility. F₄₋₆ trials showed sterility levels below that of Ambalalava.

The level attained in 1991 is one of normal sterility, showing the polygenic nature of cold tolerance that prolonged action until F₈; the parents are evidently not adapted, but they are good breeding lines for cold tolerance.

The bulk population method is efficient for determining this kind of selection. ■